

TEACHING RUSSIA IN THE ESP CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

The method of teaching foreign languages is a system of knowledge about the laws of the process of teaching a foreign language and the ways to influence this process in order to optimize it. Teaching method foreign language opens and substantiates the laws of foreign language teaching. Historically, there were two functionally different methods: General and private methods. The General technique, as a rule, is devoted to the study of the laws and features of the process of learning a foreign language, regardless of what foreign language in question. Thus, the principles of selection of educational material, the ratio of oral and written speech at different stages of the lesson, etc. they will be the same for any of the Western European languages studied in secondary schools of our country in equivalent conditions of education.

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KEY WORDS

General and private methods, learning process, educational process.

Introduction

However, knowledge of the General laws of teaching foreign language insufficient when the teacher is faced with the specific features of a particular foreign language. Thus, the ways of mastering the verbal forms of Continuous are specific only for the English language, cumbersome models of word composition, declension of nouns and adjectives are typical for the German language, and the methods of formation of numerals, the use of diacritics, the reduction of the article, the presence of a part-time article – in French. Significant differences are observed in phonetics: for the English language specific diphthongs and diphthongs, for French – nasal vowels. As experience and practice shows, the teacher needs to develop and implement such techniques, methods and forms of training that contributed to the rapid

mastery of students relevant specific phenomena in a particular foreign language. Thus, the private method explores the teaching of language and speech phenomena that are specific to a particular study of foreign language. General and private methods are interrelated. General method it is enriched on the basis of experience of private techniques. In turn, the laws of the General technique are reflected in the private. The subject of foreign language teaching methods is the accumulated knowledge about the object, a numerous theory that models the learning process; it is the laws of the learning process of foreign language. The basic concepts that make up the Foundation of the methodology include: process, goals, content, principles, methods, techniques, tools and organizational forms of training. The

purpose of training is what we strive for in the process of learning foreign language, it is an ideally planned result [3]. First, the goal of training is set, only then the methodology is developed. The purpose of training is closely related to learning conditions, as without them it is impossible to achieve.

Main part

Learning conditions are the circumstances under which learning takes place. The means of training are the tools of the educational process, with which more successfully and in a short time achieved the goals. The means of training include: textbook, workbook, tape recorder, cards. All of the above categories serve the learning system – a universal model of the educational process, corresponding to a certain methodological concept. Training system – a complete set of components corresponding to a certain methodological concept; it defines the goals, content, principles, methods, techniques, methods, means, forms of organization of training and, in turn, is determined by them. The system of teaching a foreign language is based on the provisions of the universal connection and interdependence of the phenomena of reality, the integrity of the continuously developing world and the systematic reflection of our knowledge about it. The integrity of the system is ensured by a variety of links between its elements and their interaction in the functioning of the system. With regard to the teaching of foreign languages, it is advisable to consider the concept of the system at two levels: at the level of the most significant phenomena and processes that determine the initial provisions of the methodology of teaching foreign languages; at the level of the pedagogical process, that

is, the activities of teachers and students, mediated by the educational complex, which determines the end result — a certain degree of training. The connection with linguistics is important and necessary for the methodology. The subject of training is the training of speech activity on the material of language. Linguistics also describes the basic system properties of a particular language, formulates them in the rules that are active the method is used in the development of specific training models. The technique is in close connection with psychology. The technique uses the data of psychological science about the peculiarities of perception in teaching a foreign language, the role of thinking and its connection with language, the ratio of conscious and unconscious (a combination of arbitrary and involuntary attention, awareness and imitation), the formation of skills and abilities, motivation of educational activities, etc. In its provisions, the technique is based on the study of L. S. Vygotsky, S. L. Rubinstein, A. N. Leontief, in which the developed theory of action, especially mental activity, draws the data on the memory issues, formation of skills, mechanisms of speech, is taken into account the theory of installation. Great contribution to the development of the techniques introduced scholars who dedicated works to the development of foreign language teaching. The merit of V. A. Artemov, B. A. Belyaev and other psychologists is that they not only approved speech as an object of learning, but also gave a psychological justification for the need to teach speech in all forms in a foreign language. Based on the General psychology, pedagogical psychology, psychology of learning a foreign language, the technique draws from them data on the

psychological characteristics of speech, speech and written, external and internal. It is undeniable that using the General psychological concepts of formation of skills and abilities in the activity, the technique clarifies them on the material of their own subject and enriches the General psychological theory of activity with such specific categories as speech skill, speech ability. Therefore, the connection of the methodology with psychology should be understood not as an elementary use of the methodology of psychological theory, but as a bilateral dialectical relationship, contributing to the mutual clarification, addition and enrichment of theories both Sciences. Before the technique, the following problems are identified: – definition of a foreign language as a subject; – the study of the teacher (development of forms, methods, techniques trainings); – the study activities of a student (verification of the effectiveness methods used, the study of the development of the student); – the establishment of specific laws, the definition of the scope the action of laws related to the methodology of science and identify them specific refraction in the technique. It is obvious that the process of learning foreign language speech is extremely multidimensional. Motivation in learning a foreign language is an internal driving force that makes a person spend time and effort on learning a foreign language. Foreign languages are becoming one of the main factors of socio-economic and cultural progress of society. Educational motivation can be divided into positive and negative. So, the construction of "if I will learn English, I will get an excellent exam" is a positive motivation. However, the construction of "if I learn

English, I will pass the exam and I will not be expelled" – negative. Motivation can also be divided into external and internal. External motivation is not directly related to the content of the subject, but is due to external circumstances (being an excellent student in all subjects and tries to have a foreign language "excellent" – an external positive motive; the student learns a foreign language because of the fear of strict parents or teachers – external negative motive). External motivation exists in two varieties: broad social motivation and narrow-minded. External motivation "of the process of teaching is associated with a rather keenly felt sense of civic duty to the country, to dear, close people, is associated with the idea of teaching as a road to the development of great values of culture, with the idea of teaching as a way to implement its purpose in life." European Journal of Business & Social Sciences Available at <https://ejbss.org/> ISSN: 2235-767X Volume 07 Issue 05 May 2019 Available online:<https://ejbss.org/> P a g e | 614 Narrow-minded external motivation determines the attitude to mastering a foreign language as a way of self-assertion, and sometimes as a way to personal well-being. Internal motivation is not related to external circumstances, but directly to the object itself. It is often called procedural motivation. Varieties of internal motivation: motivation associated with the long-term development of personality; communicative motivation; motivation generated by the educational activities. Conclusion: to acquaint students with the basic provisions of modern methods of teaching foreign languages; to show the connection of methods with other Sciences, which are basic for the methodology and

largely determine its current content and status among other General education and scientific disciplines; to form students' ability to evaluate existing concepts of teaching foreign languages; to acquaint students with the techniques, methods,

means of training and to form the ability to effectively and creatively apply them in practice; to give a holistic view of the nature and specificity of the professional activity of a foreign language teacher

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